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ABSTRACTS

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Construction and analysis of Co-Expression Network associated with Abiotic stress responses in *Sorghum bicolor*

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Abstract: Abiotic stress has a major impact on the development and yield of *Sorghum bicolor*. Investigating the gene expression profiles under abiotic stress may help us understand molecular mechanisms of plants to cope with unfavourable conditions. In the current study, system-level analysis was performed by establishing a gene co-expression network on the basis of several RNA-seq datasets which are easily accessible in public domain. The aim of our research is to find key players involved in stress responsive pathways. This study is the first of its kind, based on abiotic stress related condition dependent co-expression network in *Sorghum bicolor*. 6593 DEGs were identified in three different abiotic stress conditions. Co-expression network was constructed using Weighted Gene Co-Expression Network Analysis (WGCNA) with 21 high throughput samples from 3 dissimilar experimental conditions. 12 co-expressed modules were identified out of which 4 showed specific functional enrichments in abiotic stress responsive pathways. 9 hub genes were identified in the 4 modules and GO analysis revealed their response to temperature stimulus, cold, sulphur starvation, heat, lithium ion, alcohol, lipids, chemical, oxygen-containing compound. Altogether the study provided better insights of key regulators corresponding with abiotic stress reciprocation in *Sorghum bicolor*. Furthermore, metabolic pathways and genes identified here can act as esteemed genetic resources for more distant functional validation experiments.

Keywords: *Sorghum bicolor*, abiotic stress, RNA-seq, DEG, co-expression networks, hub genes.

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